

Energy and Flexibility Modelling

Hands-on 2 (macOS)

Please use the following citation for:

- **This exercise**

Tan, N., Cannone, C., Kell, A., Howells, M. (2022, January). Hands-on 2 (macOS): Energy and Flexibility Modelling. <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5920425>

- **clicSANDMac Software**

Cannone, C., Tan, N., Kell, A., de Wet, N., Howells, M., Yeganyan, R. (2021). clicSANDMac [computer software]. <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5879056>

- **OSeMOSYS Google Forum**

Please sign up to the help Google forum [here](#). If you are stuck, please ask questions here. If you get ahead, please answer questions in the same forum. Please state that you are using the 'clicSAND' Interface.

Learning outcomes

By the end of this exercise, you will be able to:

1. Create a new model in the SAND Interface
2. Learn the main functionalities of the SAND Interface
3. Define the duration of Timeslices
4. Add Year Split values
5. Check Depreciation Method and Discount Rate values

Create a new model

After installing the software and downloading the files needed (as in [Hands-on 1](#)), you can now create your first model in OSeMOSYS using the interface named SAND. This is an Excel-based (Macro-Enabled) file where you can input the data needed for OSeMOSYS to find the optimal solution to your problem. Let's learn how to save and manage your files.

1. Create a folder called **"HO2"** for this Hands-On 2.
2. Go to your 'Applications' folder and double-click on 'clisANDMac' to open the software.

3. This screen will show up. Click on 'Export Templates' and direct it to the HO2 folder you created in Step 1.

4. This will automatically save a blank copy of four files:

File name	Description	Action to take
CCG-SAND Interface v.12.xlsm	Excel Macro Enabled Workbook	Rename the file to SAND_Interface_HO2
OSeMOSYS_code.txt	Text file. This is the code needed to run your models	Nothing. We do not need to change it
Results Database.accdb	Access database to store the results obtained	Nothing. We will not use this file
ResultsTemplate.xlsm	Excel Macro Enabled Workbook	Nothing. We will not use this file

Tip: Every time you make substantial changes to your model, save it as a new version in the correspondent folder. For example, if I want to test different options on my Hands-On 2 file, I will create a new file in the folder “**HO2**” called “**SAND_Interface_HO2_v2**” and so on.

Repeat these steps for each Hands-On (New Hox folder -> Open clicSANDMac -> Export Templates in the HOx folder)

Important: The files should not be saved or synced in One Drive for clicSAND to work

You now know how to manage your folders and files!

Main functionalities of SAND Interface

The next step is to learn how to use the SAND Interface. **Don't worry**, it looks more complicated than it really is.

1. Open the renamed file **SAND_Interface_HO2**

2. A pop-up will appear. Click on 'Enable Macros'.

3. You will now see an Excel Workbook with four Sheets – **Naming**, **SETS**, **Parameters**, and **ToDataFile**. The Sheets **SETS**, **Parameters**, and **ToDataFile** represent the core of the Interface, and they are entirely interconnected to one another.

Core Sheets

4. Go to **SETS** - this is the place where you can define the name of your **Technologies** (in column B), **Commodities** (in column E) and **Emissions** (in column H).

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I
1			Technologies			Commodities			Emissions
2		Code	Description		Code	Description		Code	Description
3		TEC000	Additional Technology		COM001	Additional Fuel		EMIC02	Emission factor for CO2
4		TEC001	Additional Technology		COM002	Additional Fuel		EMICH4	Emission factor for methane
5		TEC002	Additional Technology		COM003	Additional Fuel		EMIFGA	Emission factor for Fluorinated gases
6		TEC003	Additional Technology		COM004	Additional Fuel		EMIN2O	Emission factor for Nitrous Oxide
7		TEC004	Additional Technology		COM005	Additional Fuel		EMIREN	Emission factor for RET targets
8		TEC005	Additional Technology		COM006	Additional Fuel		Region	
9		TEC006	Additional Technology		COM007	Additional Fuel		RE1	Region 1
10		TEC007	Additional Technology		COM008	Additional Fuel		ResultsPath "C:\...\res.csv" (change it before running)	
11		TEC008	Additional Technology		COM009	Additional Fuel		="C:\Users\Carla\Desktop\runs\2020\UN\CLEW50\2\res.csv";	
12		TEC009	Additional Technology		COM010	Additional Fuel			
13		TEC010	Additional Technology		COM011	Additional Fuel			
14		TEC011	Additional Technology		COM012	Additional Fuel			
15		TEC012	Additional Technology		COM013	Additional Fuel			

These three columns are linked to the 'ToDataFile' Sheet that has the format needed by the solver to find the optimal solution. Therefore, whenever you specify the name of a Technology, Commodity, or Emission in these columns, it is automatically reported in their respective cells in the 'ToDataFile' Sheet.

You have the freedom to change the names **as many times as necessary** without losing the data previously added for that specific entry.

Important: Technologies, Commodities and Emissions codes in your model should be named following the guidelines explained in **Lecture 3**.

3.1 Naming Convention

3.1.5 OSeMOSYS Naming Convention Part 2

Sectors

Power: PWR
 Industry: IND
 Residential: RES
 Transport: TRA
 Agriculture: AGR
 Commerce: COM
 Cooking Stoves: STV
 Mining/Extraction: MIN
 Transformation: UPS
 Imports: IMP

Commodities

Biomass: BIO Geothermal: GEO
 Coal: COA Heat: HET
 Natural gas: NGS Hydro: HYD
 Diesel: DSL Bagasse: BAG
 Fuel oil: HFO Kerosene: KER
 Uranium: URN Solar energy: SOL
 Waste: WAS Wind energy: WND
 Charcoal: CHC Liquid petroleum gas: LNG
 Crude Oil: CRU Other hydrocarbons: OHC

Electricity before transmission: ELC001
 Electricity after transmission: ELC002

5. Go to **Parameters** - this is a giant Sheet where you will be adding data for each OSeMOSYS parameter. To make things easier and faster for you, there are filters at the top of each column where you can filter for either **Parameter (column A)**, **Technology (Column C)**, **Commodities/Fuel (Column F)**. Columns K to BN is where you can insert data from 2015 to 2070.

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	K	L	M	N	O	P	Q
	Parameter	REGION	TECHNOLOGY	EMISSION	MODE_OF_OPERATION	FUEL	TIME_SLICE	STORAGE	REGION2	Time Independent variable	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021
2	AccumulatedAnnualDemand	RES				COM001					0	0	0	0	0	0	0
3	AccumulatedAnnualDemand	RES				COM002					0	0	0	0	0	0	0
4	AccumulatedAnnualDemand	RES				COM003					0	0	0	0	0	0	0
5	AccumulatedAnnualDemand	RES				COM004					0	0	0	0	0	0	0
6	AccumulatedAnnualDemand	RES				COM005					0	0	0	0	0	0	0
7	AccumulatedAnnualDemand	RES				COM006					0	0	0	0	0	0	0
8	AccumulatedAnnualDemand	RES				COM007					0	0	0	0	0	0	0
9	AccumulatedAnnualDemand	RES				COM008					0	0	0	0	0	0	0
10	AccumulatedAnnualDemand	RES				COM009					0	0	0	0	0	0	0
11	AccumulatedAnnualDemand	RES				COM010					0	0	0	0	0	0	0
12	AccumulatedAnnualDemand	RES				COM011					0	0	0	0	0	0	0
13	AccumulatedAnnualDemand	RES				COM012					0	0	0	0	0	0	0
14	AccumulatedAnnualDemand	RES				COM013					0	0	0	0	0	0	0
15	AccumulatedAnnualDemand	RES				COM014					0	0	0	0	0	0	0
16	AccumulatedAnnualDemand	RES				COM015					0	0	0	0	0	0	0
17	AccumulatedAnnualDemand	RES				COM016					0	0	0	0	0	0	0
18	AccumulatedAnnualDemand	RES				COM017					0	0	0	0	0	0	0
19	AccumulatedAnnualDemand	RES				COM018					0	0	0	0	0	0	0
20	AccumulatedAnnualDemand	RES				COM019					0	0	0	0	0	0	0
21	AccumulatedAnnualDemand	RES				COM020					0	0	0	0	0	0	0
22	AccumulatedAnnualDemand	RES				COM021					0	0	0	0	0	0	0
23	AccumulatedAnnualDemand	RES				COM022					0	0	0	0	0	0	0
24	AccumulatedAnnualDemand	RES				COM023					0	0	0	0	0	0	0
25	AccumulatedAnnualDemand	RES				COM024					0	0	0	0	0	0	0
26	AccumulatedAnnualDemand	RES				COM025					0	0	0	0	0	0	0
27	AccumulatedAnnualDemand	RES				COM026					0	0	0	0	0	0	0
28	AccumulatedAnnualDemand	RES				COM027					0	0	0	0	0	0	0
29	AccumulatedAnnualDemand	RES				COM028					0	0	0	0	0	0	0
30	AccumulatedAnnualDemand	RES				COM029					0	0	0	0	0	0	0
31	AccumulatedAnnualDemand	RES				COM030					0	0	0	0	0	0	0
32	AccumulatedAnnualDemand	RES				COM031					0	0	0	0	0	0	0
33	AccumulatedAnnualDemand	RES				COM032					0	0	0	0	0	0	0
34	AccumulatedAnnualDemand	RES				COM033					0	0	0	0	0	0	0
35	AccumulatedAnnualDemand	RES				COM034					0	0	0	0	0	0	0
36	AccumulatedAnnualDemand	RES				COM035					0	0	0	0	0	0	0
37	AccumulatedAnnualDemand	RES				COM036					0	0	0	0	0	0	0
38	AccumulatedAnnualDemand	RES				COM037					0	0	0	0	0	0	0
39	AccumulatedAnnualDemand	RES				COM038					0	0	0	0	0	0	0
40	AccumulatedAnnualDemand	RES				COM039					0	0	0	0	0	0	0
41	AccumulatedAnnualDemand	RES				COM040					0	0	0	0	0	0	0
42	AccumulatedAnnualDemand	RES				COM041					0	0	0	0	0	0	0
43	AccumulatedAnnualDemand	RES				COM042					0	0	0	0	0	0	0
44	AccumulatedAnnualDemand	RES				COM043					0	0	0	0	0	0	0
45	AccumulatedAnnualDemand	RES				COM044					0	0	0	0	0	0	0
46	AccumulatedAnnualDemand	RES				COM045					0	0	0	0	0	0	0
47	AccumulatedAnnualDemand	RES				COM046					0	0	0	0	0	0	0
48	AccumulatedAnnualDemand	RES				COM047					0	0	0	0	0	0	0
49	AccumulatedAnnualDemand	RES				COM048					0	0	0	0	0	0	0
50	AccumulatedAnnualDemand	RES				COM049					0	0	0	0	0	0	0
51	AccumulatedAnnualDemand	RES				COM050					0	0	0	0	0	0	0

6. In **Parameters (Column A)**, filter for **YearSplit**. You will see that only data associated with the parameter called YearSplit are shown. You can add as many filters as you want. Play around with the filters and get confident with this functionality!

This is what you will see if you filter out for the Parameter **Year Split**:

Parameter	REGION	TECHNOLOGY	EMISSION	MODE_OF_OPERATION	FUEL	THRESHOLD	STORAGE	REGION2	Time Independent variable	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021
48802 YearSplit									S101	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
48803 YearSplit									S102	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
48804 YearSplit									S103	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
48805 YearSplit									S104	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
48806 YearSplit									S105	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
48807 YearSplit									S106	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
48808 YearSplit									S107	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
48809 YearSplit									S108	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
48810 YearSplit									S109	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
48811 YearSplit									S110	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
48812 YearSplit									S111	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
48813 YearSplit									S112	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
48814 YearSplit									S113	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
48815 YearSplit									S114	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
48816 YearSplit									S115	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
48817 YearSplit									S116	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
48818 YearSplit									S117	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
48819 YearSplit									S118	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
48820 YearSplit									S119	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
48821 YearSplit									S120	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
48822 YearSplit									S121	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
48823 YearSplit									S122	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
48824 YearSplit									S123	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
48825 YearSplit									S124	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
48826 YearSplit									S201	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
48827 YearSplit									S202	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
48828 YearSplit									S203	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
48829 YearSplit									S204	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
48830 YearSplit									S205	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
48831 YearSplit									S206	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
48832 YearSplit									S207	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
48833 YearSplit									S208	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
48834 YearSplit									S209	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
48835 YearSplit									S210	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
48836 YearSplit									S211	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
48837 YearSplit									S212	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
48838 YearSplit									S213	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
48839 YearSplit									S214	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
48840 YearSplit									S215	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
48841 YearSplit									S216	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
48842 YearSplit									S217	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
48843 YearSplit									S218	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
48844 YearSplit									S219	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
48845 YearSplit									S220	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
48846 YearSplit									S221	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
48847 YearSplit									S222	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
48848 YearSplit									S223	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
48849 YearSplit									S224	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
48850 YearSplit									S301	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
48851 YearSplit									S302	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

You see that from column K to column BN there are default values added. In this case, it is 0. We will add data for YearSplit at the end of this Hands-On.

- Go to **ToDataFile** - this Sheet has the format needed by the solver to find the optimal solution to your problem.

Parameter	REGION	TECHNOLOGY	EMISSION	MODE_OF_OPERATION	FUEL	THRESHOLD	STORAGE	REGION2	Time Independent variable	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024	2025	2026	2027	2028	2029	2030	2031	2032
48802 YearSplit									S101	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
48803 YearSplit									S102	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
48804 YearSplit									S103	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
48805 YearSplit									S104	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
48806 YearSplit									S105	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
48807 YearSplit									S106	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
48808 YearSplit									S107	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
48809 YearSplit									S108	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
48810 YearSplit									S109	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
48811 YearSplit									S110	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
48812 YearSplit									S111	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
48813 YearSplit									S112	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
48814 YearSplit									S113	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
48815 YearSplit									S114	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
48816 YearSplit									S115	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
48817 YearSplit									S116	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
48818 YearSplit									S117	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
48819 YearSplit									S118	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
48820 YearSplit									S119	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
48821 YearSplit									S120	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
48822 YearSplit									S121	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
48823 YearSplit									S122	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
48824 YearSplit									S123	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
48825 YearSplit									S124	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
48826 YearSplit									S201	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
48827 YearSplit									S202	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
48828 YearSplit									S203	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
48829 YearSplit									S204	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
48830 YearSplit									S205	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
48831 YearSplit									S206	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
48832 YearSplit									S207	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
48833 YearSplit									S208	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
48834 YearSplit									S209	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
48835 YearSplit									S210	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
48836 YearSplit									S211	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
48837 YearSplit									S212	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
48838 YearSplit									S213	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
48839 YearSplit									S214	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
48840 YearSplit									S215	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
48841 YearSplit									S216	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
48842 YearSplit									S217	0																	

Important: never add data to this **ToDataFile** Sheet - data should only be added to the **Parameters** and **SETS** sheets. The interface is made up in a way that all the entries will be automatically read by the **ToDataFile** sheet.

8. **Go to Naming** – here you will find the description of the parameters used in SAND Interface. Note that we are not going to use all the parameters listed here.

Welcome to the OSeMOSYS' documentation!
OSeMOSYS
Open Source Energy Modelling System
RTH - JRC, www.osemosys.org

Descriptions of SETS/Parameters/Variables used in SAND Interface from OSeMOSYS
(<https://osemosys.readthedocs.io/en/latest/manual/Structure%20of%20OSeMOSYS.html>)

Important Note: NOT all the Sets, Parameters and Variables presented here are used in SAND Interface.

Name	Description	Index
YEAR	It represents the time frame of the model, it contains all the years to be considered in the study.	1
TECHNOLOGY	It includes any element of the energy system that changes a commodity from one form to another, uses it or supplies it. All system components are set up as a "technology" in OSeMOSYS. As the model is an abstraction, the modeller is free to interpret the role of a technology as well, where relevant. It may for example represent a single root technology (such as a power plant) or can represent a nested/ aggregated collection of technologies (such as the stock of several nuclear light bulbs), or may even simply be a dummy technology, perhaps used for accounting purposes.	2
TIMEslice	It represents the time split of each modelled year, therefore the time resolution of the model. Common to several energy systems modelling tools (i.e. MESSAGE / MARKAL / TIMES), the annual demand is "sliced" into representative fractions of the year. It is necessary to assess times of the year when demand is high separately from times when demand is low, for fuels that are expensive to store. In order to reduce the computation time, these "slices" are often grouped. Thus, the annual demand may be split into aggregate seasons where demand levels are similar (such as "summer, winter and intermediate"). These seasons may be subdivided into aggregate "day types" (such as workdays and weekends), and the day further sub-divided (such as into day and night) depending on the level of demand.	3
FUEL	It includes any energy vector, energy service or process entering or exiting technologies. These can be aggregate groups, individual flows or artificially separated, depending on the requirements of the analysis.	4
EMISSION	It includes any kind of emission potentially deriving from the operation of the defined technologies. Typical examples would include atmospheric emissions of greenhouse gases, such as CO2.	5
MODE_OF_OPERATION	It defines the number of modes of operation that the technologies can have. If a technology can have various input or output fuels and it can choose the mix (i.e. any linear combination of these input or output fuels, each mix can be accounted as a separate mode of operation. For example, a CHP plant may produce heat in one mode of operation and electricity in another.	6
REGION	It sets the regions to be modelled, e.g. different countries. For each of them, the supply-demand balances for all the energy vectors are ensured, including trades with other regions. In some occasions it might be convenient to model different countries within the same region and differentiate them simply by creating set of fuels and technologies for each of them.	7
SEASON	It gives indication (by successive numerical values) of how many seasons (e.g. winter, intermediate, summer) are accounted for and in which order. This set is needed if storage facilities are included in the model.	8
DAYTYPE	It gives indication (by successive numerical values) of how many day types (e.g. workday, weekend) are accounted for and in which order. This set is needed if storage facilities are included in the model.	9
DAILYTIMEBRACKET	It gives indication (by successive numerical values) of how many parts the day is split into (e.g. night, morning, afternoon, evening) and in which order these parts are sorted. This set is needed if storage facilities are included in the model.	10
STORAGE	It includes storage facilities in the model.	11

Define the duration of time slices

To carry out a modelling exercise with OSeMOSYS, it is necessary to assign values to the set called **Timeslices**, which represents periods of the year with a similar demand. In this model, the year was initially divided into 4 timeslices representing two periods of 6 months (two representative seasons), each of which would have similar demand. This was then further sub-divided into day and night periods, called: **Summer Day (SD)**, **Summer Night (SN)**, **Winter Day (WD)**, **Winter Night (WN)**.

However, in the SAND Interface it is possible to define up to 96 timeslices, so these initial data were manipulated to obtain a 24-hour representation of a reference day for each of SD, SN, WD, and WN (24 hours each * 4 = 96 timeslices). Therefore, each year is divided into 96 periods instead of the previous 4.

It was assumed each season has an equal length, with an average hourly split per season (24hr representative), therefore obtaining:

$$4 \text{ Seasons/year} * 24\text{hr of a representative day/season} = 96 \text{ Timeslices/Year}$$

Each Timeslice represents an equal fraction of the Year in the following way, defined as the Year Split:

$$1 \text{ Year} / 96 \text{ Timeslices} = 0.0104$$

Therefore, you should add this number to the Year Split column for each year.

Tip: To help you deal with all the data, there is a [Data Preparation Spreadsheet](#) that will allow you to copy-paste the data in a faster way.

Add Year Split values

After defining the duration of each time slice and calculating the Year Split profile we need to add these values in the SAND Interface.

1. Go to the Parameters Sheet and filter for **YearSplit** (in Column A).
2. Click on this link to open the [Data Preparation Spreadsheet](#).
3. At the bottom of the webpage, you will see a tab called 'Files'. Click on Download beside **Data_Prep_HO2.xlsx**

The screenshot shows the OpenAIRE interface for the resource 'Energy and Flexibility Modelling Hands-on 2 (macOS)'. The 'Files' tab is active, displaying a table of files. The file 'Data_prep_HO2.xlsx' (15.5 kB) is highlighted, and its 'Download' button is circled in red. Other files include 'HO2_macOS.pdf' (2.0 MB). The interface also shows the OpenAIRE logo, publication date (January 30, 2022), DOI (10.5281/zenodo.5920445), and license (Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International). A 'Versions' section lists three versions of the resource, all dated January 30, 2022.

Name	Size	Download
Data_prep_HO2.xlsx	15.5 kB	Download
HO2_macOS.pdf	2.0 MB	Preview Download

- Open **Data_Prep_HO2.xlsx** once downloaded. You will see this Excel Workbook. Copy the data in Column C of the **Data Preparation File** (click on cell C2 and press on the **command key (⌘) + shift + down arrow**).

	A	B	C
1			Year Split
2	WN	S101	0.0104
3	WN	S102	0.0104
4	WN	S103	0.0104
5	WN	S104	0.0104
6	WN	S105	0.0104
7	WN	S106	0.0104
8	WD	S107	0.0104
9	HD	S108	0.0104
10	WD	S109	0.0104
11	WD	S110	0.0104
12	HD	S111	0.0104
13	WD	S112	0.0104
14	WD	S113	0.0104
15	HD	S114	0.0104
16	WD	S115	0.0104
17	WD	S116	0.0104
18	HD	S117	0.0104
19	WD	S118	0.0104
20	WN	S119	0.0104
21	WN	S120	0.0104
22	WN	S121	0.0104
23	WN	S122	0.0104
24	WN	S123	0.0104
25	WN	S124	0.0104
26	BN	S201	0.0104
27	BN	S202	0.0104
28	BN	S203	0.0104
29	BN	S204	0.0104
30	BD	S205	0.0104
31	BD	S206	0.0104
32	BD	S207	0.0104
33	BD	S208	0.0104
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35	BD	S210	0.0104
36	BD	S211	0.0104
37	BD	S212	0.0104
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318	BD	S493	0.0104
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320	BD	S495	0.0104
321	BD	S496	0.0104
322	BD	S497	0.0104</

1	Parameter	REGION	TECHNOLOGY	EMISSION	MODE_OF_OPERATION	FUEL	TIMESLICE	STORAGE	REGION2	Time independent variable	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	
4880	YearSplit									5001	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167
4881	YearSplit									5002	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167
4882	YearSplit									5003	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167
4883	YearSplit									5004	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167
4884	YearSplit									5005	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167
4885	YearSplit									5006	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167
4886	YearSplit									5007	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167
4887	YearSplit									5008	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167
4888	YearSplit									5009	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167
4889	YearSplit									5110	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167
4890	YearSplit									5111	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167
4891	YearSplit									5112	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167
4892	YearSplit									5113	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167
4893	YearSplit									5114	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167
4894	YearSplit									5115	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167
4895	YearSplit									5116	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167
4896	YearSplit									5117	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167
4897	YearSplit									5118	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167
4898	YearSplit									5119	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167
4899	YearSplit									5120	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167
4900	YearSplit									5121	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167
4901	YearSplit									5122	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167
4902	YearSplit									5123	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167
4903	YearSplit									5124	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167
4904	YearSplit									5201	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167
4905	YearSplit									5202	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167
4906	YearSplit									5203	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167
4907	YearSplit									5204	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167
4908	YearSplit									5205	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167
4909	YearSplit									5206	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167
4910	YearSplit									5207	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167
4911	YearSplit									5208	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167
4912	YearSplit									5209	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167
4913	YearSplit									5210	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167
4914	YearSplit									5211	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167
4915	YearSplit									5212	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167
4916	YearSplit									5213	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167
4917	YearSplit									5214	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167
4918	YearSplit									5215	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167
4919	YearSplit									5216	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167
4920	YearSplit									5217	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167
4921	YearSplit									5218	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167
4922	YearSplit									5219	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167
4923	YearSplit									5220	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167	0.0104167

Check Depreciation Method and Discount Rate values

We will leave default values for Depreciation Method and Discount Rate. In the future, you are free to change them following these steps.

1. Go to the **Parameters** Sheet. In Column A, filter for '**Depreciation Method**' and '**Discount Rate**'. You will see the following. Do not change these numbers, we will use these defaults values.

1	Parameter	REGION	TECHNOLOGY	EMISSION	MODE_OF_OPERATION	FUEL	TIMESLICE	STORAGE	REGION2	Time independent variable	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021
15962	DepreciationMethod	RE1								1							
15963	DiscountRate	RE1								0.1							

The **Depreciation Method** will have a value of 1 and the **Discount Rate** of 0.1 (10% discount rate). These are time independent variables; you will therefore see their value in Column J. When a variable is time dependent instead, no values will be in Column J and there will be a value for each of the modelling years (Column K to Column BN).

Name	Description
YearSplit	Duration of a modelled time slice, expressed as a fraction of the year. The sum of each entry over one modelled year should equal 1.
DiscountRate	Region specific value for the discount rate, expressed in decimals (e.g. 0.1)
DepreciationMethod	Binary parameter defining the type of depreciation to be applied. It has value 1 for sinking fund depreciation, value 2 for straight-line depreciation.

2. Save your **SAND_Interface_HO2** file. We will continue with file in Hands-On 3.
-